

A Study of Postcolonial Society in Ruth Praver Jhabvala's Heat and Dust

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Abstract

Ruth Praver Jhabvala has as a literary artist. She is a European. Her novels deal with the themes like love, sex, and marriage in the bourgeois society, East-West encounter, pseudo-modernism in Indian society, the post-independence Indian ethos, affectation and hypocrisy in the Indian middle-class society. Jhabvala's literary works are concerned with the postcolonial situation of the lives of Europeans. Her novel Heat and Dust presents outrageous human relations through the power of romance set in two distinct eras, colonial India of the 1920s, during the time of Raj and the independent, freewheeling India of the 1970s. The human relations can refer to at least two groups of people: those with mixed Indian and British ancestry. The first story is about Olivia. Olivia Rivers is a young lady from London who has accompanied her husband to British colonial India. The second story is that of the narrator, a descendant of Douglas, and his second wife. The novel deals the story with enough romance, political, and history. We have encountered the characters - the heat, dust, poverty, superstition, British postcolonial administrators. Thus, it explores human relations through the power of romance in postcolonial society.

Keywords: Indian society, the pre and the post-independence India, fashions, psychology of expatriate, and postcolonial .

Traditionally women have excelled in all walks of life. In the field of literature, they have made debut due to their superior imagination and sense and sensibility. The novelists have given a new dimension to the Indian Literature. They have incorporated the recurring female experiences in their writings, and it affected the cultural and language patterns of Indian Literature. Their novels/fictions consist of the latest burning issues related to women as well as those issues that exist in society. Ruth Praver Jhabvala has as a literary artist. She is a European. Her novels deal with the themes like love, sex, and marriage in the bourgeois society, East-West encounter, pseudo-modernism , the post-independence Indian ethos, affectation and hypocrisy in the Indian middle-class. She handles her ideas with presents a penetrating and a compassionate picture of human relationship.

Jhabvala's literary works are concerned with the diasporic postcolonial situation of the lives of Europeans. Her works abound with female characters struggling to survive in the unfamiliar surroundings and situations. She deals with the common problems, loneliness and fulfillment.

Jhabvala's novel *Heat and Dust* presents outrageous human relations through the power of romance set in two distinct eras, colonial India of the 1920s, during the time of Raj and the independent, freewheeling India of the 1970s. The human relations can refer to at least two groups of people: those with mixed Indian and British ancestry, and people of British descent born or living in the Indian subcontinent. The people were the product of the confident European expansion of the 16th century. In the years of British colonial, intermarriage between the British and the native females was encouraged. But soon after British power was establishing in India, this policy had reversed: it was feared that a mixed community might threaten the British rule.

The Novel *Heat and Dust* tell two parallel stories about two ladies in different periods and their adventures in India. The first story is about Olivia Rivers. Olivia is a young beautiful lady from London. She has accompanied her husband to British colonial India. She comes to India in the conventional role of a wife to the sub-collector of Satipur. Her husband Douglas Rivers is an English ICS Officer. She is spoiled, and spirited young woman beauty. She finds it difficult to adjust to life in the British colonial community of Satipur. Douglas's official duty, he spends very little time with his wife. Olivia loves her husband very much, but she feels suffocated by the inbred group. She longs for independence, intellectual stimulation, and more passionate life. She is suffocated by the social constraints of her position as the wife of an important English civil servant. She hopes that a baby will solve her problems, but finds it more difficult to become pregnant than she has thought. In India, Douglas, Olivia and some of the other members of the community has invited to the palace of the Nawab of Khatm. Olivia is drawn passion and independence into the spell of the Nawab of khatm. The Nawab is extremely attractive and handsome. She is intrigued by the Nawab's charm and aggressive courtship. She begins to spend most of her days in his company. Soon she develops her friendship turns passionate. She makes frequent visits to the place of Nawab.

The Nawab is deeply involved in gang raids and criminal plots. Harry informs this shocking news to Olivia: "When we go from here, Olivia, will you go back to Satipur and say yes, the Nawab is a bad person, now I have seen with my own eyes that he meets with outlaws, dacoits he is hand in glove with them." (147) The Nawab is the ruler of a state. He has drained the exchequer of the poor state of its last pie by his vulgar extravagance. Also, when the state coffers are not in a position to support his decadent style of living. He joins notorious bandits to rob and plunders his people. Olivia's experience in India is limited to the Nawab. He gives her a sense of belonging and the kind of importance that flatters her ego. Her illicit relations with the Nawab after she gets the results into pregnancy. Olivia has ever known to become the lover. She hides the fact of her pregnancy from her husband: "When Olivia found that she was pregnant, she didn't tell Douglas. She put it off from day to day, and in the end it happened that she told the Nawab first." (154-155) Olivia tries an abortion with the help of the Nawab's friend, Harry. Douglas divorces her when he comes to know about the affair. Then he remarries, and Olivia remains in India for the rest of her life. Olivia then resides in Town X for her remaining years.

In the second story is that of the narrator, a descendant of Douglas, and his second wife. His wife arrives in Bombay intending to make it her home for a while. She wants to reconstruct the story of the doomed marriage of her grandfather, Douglas and his first wife, Olivia. She presents her adventures, thoughts, and reflection in the form of a journal. She tries her best to discover what motivates Olivia to change her life. She stays in the town where her grandfather and Olivia fifty years before. She has portraits of India. She accepts the sick and deformed men of Satipur as part of the landscape. She visits the places her step- grandmother. She also interviews people who know of her. Certainly, she adopts to live her life in the Olivia way. Her subject of research slowly widens from Olivia's life in India to herself in India. She reads the letters and journals that Olivia wrote so

long ago. She ventures into experiences similar to Olivia's adventures but more acceptable in our modern time. Her spiritual and sensual journey in the 1970s parallels Olivia's like the colour, heat, exotic landscapes, and people of India penetrate her western upbringing. Anne writes in her own diary: "Fortunately, during my first few months here, I kept a journal, so I have some record of my early impressions. If I were to try to recollect them now, I might not be able to do so. They are no longer the same because I myself am no longer the same. India always changes people, and I have been no exception."(2)

In this novel, the protagonist Olivia falls in love with an Indian man. He is a clerk named Inder Lal. He comes from the lower middle-class, and he is a representative specimen of the new India. In this role, he offers a contrast to the Rajas and Nawabs of British India. He is married, and Ritu is his wife, but he develops a relationship with the narrator. His relationship with Anne is an only a mechanical one. He makes her pregnant. Unconsciously, Anne falls the same path of her step-grandmother. As Olivia did, she also has an Anglo-Indian love affair and picks up where Olivia left. She has a casual attitude to her pregnancy. Unlike Olivia, she decides to have a child of Inder Lal. At the end of the novel, she decides to spend her years in Town X, just as Olivia did, "I have taken a room in the town of X and live there in the same way I did in Satipur. The town is the same too — the houses are ramshackle, the alleys intricate and narrow; only here everything is on slope, so that it looks as if the whole town might slide down the mountain any minute."(196) When we analyze text, we can find out that both Olivia and Anne led the same life. Olivia seeks merger into Indian through sex but remains to suffer. She does not return to England but stays in a house upon hills. Then she hopes to find the resolution of the conflict of two cultures. But the narrator is different from Olivia in some matters. She imbibes the spirit of the land; she naturally identifies herself with India. She offers an image of India which contrasts the fragmentation and alienation of the West. To her, India is a big country that accommodates many ideas and things which are incompatible in nature, "Town is used to accepting and merging all sorts of different elements for instance, the grand old tombs of Mohammedan royalty on the one hand and the little grey suttee stones on the other. There are also the town's cripples idiots and resident beggars". (78-79) Olivia consents to abort the child in her step-grandmother. Anne is determined to have her baby. Both of them have the influence of Anglo-Indian culture. They fall under India's spell. Jhabvala observes that India is a magnet for Europeans in search of a spirituality that they have failed to find in western religions.

A study of the technique of two parallel narratives within one narrative also helps in setting up a comparative study of Indian society, and the possibility of analyzing two different racial relations living with passion in two 'Indias' - the pre-independence India and the post-independence India of the postcolonial society. In the narrative, two-time frames are running parallel to each other, and sometimes, they merge into each other too. There are some occasions when the time frame of one narrative merges with the second narrative. At the surface level, events and situations in both the stories are quite similar, but the attitude of the narrator while narrating two different narratives is not so. Two similar seeming plots end in different fashions. This technique of juxtaposing seemingly similar events of two parallel narratives helps in establishing a relation of similarity between the two fabulous happenings in two different time frames and allows the reader to have the advantage of the comparative study of the postcolonial society. The narrative gives insight into the psychology of the expatriate as both the women in the plots are dislocated from their original land and go through the romantic encounter in a foreign land. It also reveals the narrator's impression about India, as the narrator is also present in the narrative as a character.

Thus, Jhabvala's *Heat and Dust* deals the story with enough romance, political, and history. We have encountered in almost every scene and character - the heat, dust, poverty, superstition, the

rigidly emotional British postcolonial administrators, the catty British wives, the noble and rogue natives, the reaction of British men and women who are seduced by the setting scandalizing the communities. All the characters were realistic. It is the presentation of Indian society. It explores human relations through the power of romance in postcolonial society.

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